

Semantic interoperable data model and stochastic multiscale analysis of short fibre composites

Jörg Hohe, Benedikt Rohrmüller, Patrick Schneider, Niklas Toffert,
Martin Koerdel, Nicolas Christ, Carla Beckmann

- Introduction
- Experimental observation
- Numerical homogenisation and stochastic enhancement
- Semantic interoperable data model
- Example
- Conclusions

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Introduction

- microstructural uncertainties in composite and other microheterogeneous materials

- uncertain fibre orientation, length, density, bundle formation, ...
- uncertain particle / void size, shape, density, ...
- uncertain constituent material properties
- uncertain distribution of defects, delaminations, interface properties, crack formation, ...

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Experimental observation

- example: PA66 GF40
- stress-strain response
- overall
 - tensile tests within and perpendicular to flow direction
 - section 10 mm x 3 mm
 - overall scatter
- local
 - grey scale correlation system (ARAMIS)
 - distinct scatter on length scales below 10 mm

overall stress-strain response

longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Numerical homogenisation

- concept of the representative volume element

- energy based equivalence conditions

$$\bar{w} = \frac{1}{V^{RVE}} \int_{\Omega^{RVE}} w \, dV = \frac{1}{V^{RVE}} \int_{\Omega^{RVE*}} w^* \, dV^*$$

$$\bar{F}_{ij} = \frac{1}{V^{RVE}} \int_{\Omega^{RVE}} F_{ij} \, dV = \frac{1}{V^{RVE}} \int_{\Omega^{RVE*}} F_{ij}^* \, dV^*$$

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Numerical homogenisation

discussion

requirements for the representative volume element

- $L \gg l \gg dl$
- l sufficiently large to account for all possible microstructural effects
- l sufficiently small for RVE representing a macroscopic material point

typical characteristic length scales for short fibre composites

- $l_{\text{micro}} = 100 \mu\text{m}, \dots, 500 \mu\text{m} \Rightarrow l = 1 \text{ mm}, \dots, 5 \text{ mm}$
- $L \geq 2 \text{ mm}, \dots, 25 \text{ mm}$
 - requirements might be contradictory
 - statistically representative volume element might not exist
 - probabilistic assessment required

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Numerical homogenisation

- alternative
 - approaches for assessment of the material uncertainty caused by the geometric uncertainty on the micro level
 - prediction of probability distributions for effective properties
 - probabilistic enhancement of the deterministic homogenization approach
- two different routes
 - multiple analysis of small scale testing volume elements with random microstructure
 - local homogenisation of small scale subsets in large-scale representative volume element
 - microstructure and volume related testing volume elements

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Semantic interoperable data model

- stochastic multiscale analysis requires extensive data handling
 - automated procedure required
 - holistic semantic interoperable data model
- knowledge graphs and ontologies
 - data model as directed graph
 - set of nodes, e.g., 1, 2, 3, and 4
 - set of edges, e.g., (1,2), (1,3), (3,2), (3,4), 3,4)
 - what makes a directed graph “knowledgable”?
 - everything has unique IDs called URI (except data properties)
 - knowledge graph as a set of triples including the ontology
 - syntax: triple (subject-predicate-object), where (subject, object) induces an edge and predicate is its label
 - ontologies are the scheme of a knowledge graph (giving structure to it)

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Semantic interoperable data model

- physical product and material

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Semantic interoperable data model

- modular set-up to account for uncertainties

deterministic
multiscale
analysis

stochastic elements

modular
stochastic
enhancement

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- reference material
 - injection moulded material
 - phenolic resin matrix
 - short glass fibre reinforcement

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- five different macroscopic fibre orientation states
- covering typical range for injection moulded plates
- definition in terms of second order fibre orientation tensor

$$a_{ij} = \frac{1}{n^f} \frac{1}{\sum_{q=1}^{n^f} l^{(q)}} \sum_{q=1}^{n^f} l^{(q)} r_i^{(q)} r_j^{(q)}$$

- subdivision into 6 x 6 stochastic volume elements
 - pronounced uncertainty in microstructural morphology
 - subsets with rather different microscopic orientations

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- deformation and failure
 - in-plane modes

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- stress-strain response

tensile load cases

shear load cases

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- correlation matrix

$$C(p_1, p_2) =$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{E}((p_1 - \mathcal{E}(p_1)) (p_2 - \mathcal{E}(p_2)))}{(\mathcal{E}((p_1 - \mathcal{E}(p_1))^2) \mathcal{E}((p_2 - \mathcal{E}(p_2))^2))^{1/2}}$$

	a_I	a_{II}	a_{III}	f_V	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	H_{11}	H_{22}	H_{33}	H_{12}	H_{13}	H_{23}
a_I	1.000	-0.917	-0.561	0.088	0.703	-0.365	0.022	-0.317	-0.328	-0.219	-0.038	-0.406	-0.233	0.292	-0.055	-0.313
a_{II}	-0.917	1.000	0.186	-0.055	-0.589	0.438	-0.070	0.343	0.193	0.078	-0.059	0.218	-0.035	-0.316	0.182	0.436
a_{III}	-0.561	0.186	1.000	-0.100	-0.507	-0.011	0.091	0.070	0.408	0.379	0.206	0.545	0.644	-0.055	-0.234	-0.136
f_V	0.088	-0.055	-0.100	1.000	0.505	0.325	0.559	0.555	0.329	0.398	0.245	0.131	-0.100	-0.053	0.096	-0.168
E_1	0.703	-0.589	-0.507	0.505	1.000	-0.315	0.188	-0.058	-0.040	-0.103	0.229	-0.279	-0.240	0.126	-0.071	-0.410
E_2	-0.365	0.438	-0.011	0.325	-0.315	1.000	-0.001	0.251	0.080	0.311	-0.161	0.195	-0.117	-0.080	0.175	0.205
E_3	0.022	-0.070	0.091	0.559	0.188	-0.001	1.000	0.416	0.096	0.384	0.280	0.119	0.188	-0.127	-0.134	-0.072
G_{12}	-0.317	0.343	0.070	0.555	-0.058	0.251	0.416	1.000	0.183	0.275	0.150	0.307	-0.088	-0.164	0.207	0.139
G_{13}	-0.328	0.193	0.408	0.329	-0.040	0.080	0.096	0.183	1.000	0.063	0.279	0.427	0.243	-0.230	0.099	-0.183
G_{23}	-0.219	0.078	0.379	0.398	-0.103	0.311	0.384	0.275	0.063	1.000	0.163	0.306	0.387	-0.002	0.003	0.010
H_{11}	-0.038	-0.059	0.206	0.245	0.229	-0.161	0.280	0.150	0.279	0.163	1.000	0.356	0.165	-0.456	-0.479	-0.145
H_{22}	-0.406	0.218	0.545	0.131	-0.279	0.195	0.119	0.307	0.427	0.306	0.356	1.000	0.572	-0.368	-0.223	-0.352
H_{33}	-0.233	-0.035	0.644	-0.100	-0.240	-0.117	0.188	-0.088	0.243	0.387	0.165	0.572	1.000	-0.046	-0.361	-0.445
H_{12}	0.292	-0.316	-0.055	-0.053	0.126	-0.080	-0.127	-0.164	-0.230	-0.002	-0.456	-0.368	-0.046	1.000	0.179	-0.114
H_{13}	-0.055	0.182	-0.234	0.096	-0.071	0.175	-0.134	0.207	0.099	0.003	-0.479	-0.223	-0.361	0.179	1.000	0.270
H_{23}	-0.313	0.436	-0.136	-0.168	-0.410	0.205	-0.072	0.139	-0.183	0.010	-0.145	-0.352	-0.445	-0.114	0.270	1.000

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Example

- dependence on orientation state (elastic moduli)
 - planar approximation of dependence on principal values of fibre orientation tensor
 - stochastic evaluation in terms of standard deviation of distance to approximation plane

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

Conclusions

- stochastic analysis of macroscopic material response of short fibre composites
 - interoperable data model
 - stochastic multiscale homogenization analysis
- stochastic assessment necessary due to violation of RVE size requirements
- semantic interoperable data model
 - holistic ontology for short fibre composites including entire life cycle from processing to recycling
 - modular definition enables simple integration of stochastic pre- and postprocesses
- stochastic homogenization
 - based on stochastic volume elements defined as subsets of large-scale statistically representative volume element
 - results
 - correlation of mechanical properties with fibre orientation
 - distinct local (basic) uncertainty

contribution based on two projects funded by

Bundesministerium
für Forschung, Technologie
und Raumfahrt

DFG

Interoperable data model and stochastic analysis of short fibre composites

References

- (1) Christ, N., Wittemann, F., Rohrmüller, B., Hohe, J., Kärger, L., Beckmann, C.: *Numerical Analysis of uncertainty propagation in short fiber-reinforced composites: from injection molding to material testing*, Compos. Sci. Tech. (submitted).
- (2) Koerdel, M., Milicic Brandt, M., Seidel, C., Toffert, N.A., Hohe, J.: Parametrierung und Automatisierung von Multiskalensimulationsketten für faserverstärkte Verbundwerkstoffe auf Grundlage strukturierter Materialcharakterisierungsdaten, 24th Symp. Verbundwerkstoffe und Werkstoffverbunde (Freiburg, May 22-24, 2024), electronic publication.
- (3) Rohrmüller, B., Kneisel, F., Christ, N., Hohe, J., Beckmann, C.: *Experimental investigation into the uncertainty of the mechanical properties of short fibre-reinforced polymers*, J. Compos. Sci. (submitted).
- (4) Rohrmüller, B., Christ, N., Hohe, J., Beckmann, C.: *Numerical study of the microstructure induced uncertainty in the mechanical properties of short fibre reinforced polymers*, Prob. Eng. Mech. (submitted).

Contact

PD Dr.-Ing. Jörg Hohe
Head of Composite Materials Group
Fraunhofer IWM
Wöhlerstr. 11 | 79108 Freiburg | Germany
Tel. +49 761 5142 340
joerg.hohe@iwm.fraunhofer.de